

Scalable real-time health data sensing and analysis enabling collaborative care delivery

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Abstract

This work describes a novel end-to-end data ingestion and runtime processing pipeline, which is a core part of a technical solution aiming to monitor frailty indices of patients during and after treatment and improve their quality of life. The focus of this work is on the technical architectural details and the functionalities provided, which have been developed in a manner that are extensible, scalable and fault-tolerant by design. Extensibility refers to both data sources and the exact specification of analysis techniques. Our platform can combine data not only from multiple sensor types but also from electronic health records. Also, the analysis component can process the patient data both individually and in combination with other patients, while exploiting both cloud and edge resources. We have shown concrete examples of advanced analytics and evaluated the scalability of the system, which has been fully prototyped.

Keywords: data ingestion, streaming analytics, frailty monitoring, cloud processing, edge processing

1 Introduction

Nowadays, there is an increasing need for runtime monitoring and analysis of patient behavior especially after serious treatments. For example, cancer refers to a group of diseases, where abnormal cells divide without control causing multiple health problems by invading nearby tissues. According to Eurostat, cancer is responsible for more than one quarter (25.8%) of the total number of deaths in the European Union¹. Due to such seriousness of this disease group, vast research efforts have been undertaken to develop effective and efficient treatment for cancer patients. However, these treatments usually come with a cost in terms of side-effects lasting well beyond the end of the treatment. Multiple researchers have identified various late effects of cancer treatment (Ganz, 2001; Agrawal, 2014; Schover et al, 2014; Stein et al, 2008; Lenihan and Cardinale, 2012; Balducci, 2007). Among the extended list of late effects of cancer treatment for adult populations, frailty is one of the most important ones (Ommundsen et al, 2014; Bennett et al, 2013; Ness and Wogsch, 2020; Ethun et al, 2017). This, in turn, calls for development of methodologies and platforms for the monitoring of frailty indices of patients during and after their treatment process in order to identify the reasons, discover possible correlations between effects and treatments and devise methodologies to improve the patients' Quality of Life (QoL). This need has motivated our work.

Post-cancer care including cancer survivors' follow-up and monitoring of their QoL remains an overlooked issue and is highly considered as clinician-led rather patient data-driven (Wildiers et al, 2014). However, since QoL is a highly subjective experience of patients' themselves, data generated by the patients themselves, outside the clinic, are essential. Typical examples of relevant data sources include person-reported outcomes (PROs) and person-reported experiences (PREs) (Kotronoulas et al, 2014). PROs collection is facilitated through the self-administration of validated questionnaires and their content includes the exploration of matters that cancer survivors' primarily focus on, like symptom burden (Halliday et al, 2012) including frequency of occurrence, the ability to carry on with daily activities (Graf, 2008) and daily life matters relevant to physical (Smit et al, 2020) and mental health (Reynolds and Gould, 1981). In addition to the systematic collection of PROs through mobile apps, quality of life and frailty indicators can be collected and quantified through mobile sensors (Park et al, 2021). Examples of such type of digital indicators include vocal biomarkers (Fagherazzi et al, 2021) collected through built-in microphones of smart phones and mobility patterns (Wang et al, 2021) collected using wearables or unobtrusive sensors that allow the identification of depressive symptoms (Pedrelli et al, 2020), early signs of cognitive decline (Enshaeifar et al, 2018), and several other geriatric syndromes including frailty (Zhou et al, 2021).

From the technical perspective, developing a sensing and runtime analysis platform in the Internet of Things (IoT) and Web of Things (WoT) era can take

¹<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>

full advantage of the fact that sensors are easy to be deployed and used to monitor the physical status and the activities of patients under treatment remotely, both indoors and outdoors, which implies that the platform both generates and handles a potentially massive stream of measurement data. These data, after being analysed by researchers, doctors and other medical personnel, can play an important role in treating frailty and improving the patients' QoL. Their analysis, however, involves combination of historical data, electronic health records (EHR) and data from other patients. As such, the platform needs to go beyond merely performing simple statistical analysis and rule-based checks on a set of single-type measurements, something that is possible to be executed on smartphones or smartwatches; to the contrary, it needs to both (i) enable big data management, processing and analysis, and (ii) support collaboration and information sharing between patients, healthcare professionals and caregivers.

In this work we present such a big data – driven Data Ingestion and Runtime Analysis Pipeline (DIRAP) solution. DIRAP is based on both an edge and a scalable cloud-based runtime processing engine, which can analyze the main features that affect the QoL of cancer patients during and after their treatment on the fly using statistical and Artificial Intelligence (AI) models. The contribution of this work is to provide and present the details about the different components that constitute the DIRAP, the overall architecture and the stream processing algorithms that are responsible for the analysis of the incoming streaming data. The novelty of this architecture in comparison to previous approaches is that it provides a unique combination of properties in an end-to-end solution, in order to support real-world healthcare scenarios. DIRAP is responsible for the collection, extraction, and analysis of data from different types of heterogeneous and multimodal sources, e.g., it can ingest both streaming and batch offline data. Its edge-hosted component is endowed with advanced real-time analytics capabilities before forwarding raw data to the cloud. The cloud-hosted component on the other hand, goes beyond the lambda architecture and offers a practical implementation of the kappa architecture, in which a single engine is responsible for both streaming and batch data. This enhances the extensibility and maintainability of the system. Finally, Apache Flink, which is the main framework that DIRAP was built upon, provides the essential scalability apart from supporting arbitrarily complex analytics over data stemming from multiple sources.

DIRAP has been fully implemented and used in the context of the LifeChamps project², which aims to provide such a data-driven solution capable of improving the QoL of not just patients, but healthcare professionals and caregivers as well, via a timely and more accurate clinical decision support at the point of care.

To achieve its objectives, DIRAP aims to meet the requirements below:

- R1:** Support heterogeneous and multimodal data streams or batch/offline data, ingested from multiple sources and transferred to a centralized location. The DIRAP should be constantly available to receive data from diverse sources,

²<https://lifechamps.eu/>

like measurements from wearables, location sensors, electronic health records (EHR) from hospitals, patient reported outcome measures (PROMS), etc., preprocess them and publish them to an event manager.

- R2:** Perform real time analytics and pre-processing, duplicate events removal, ensure consistency in timestamps, remove faulty measurements, and the appropriate aggregations, while facilitating the employment of available models, such as neural network ones.
- R3:** Ensure scalability and adaptivity, both horizontally (i.e., data stream volume) and vertically (i.e., number of streams).
- R4:** Guarantee fault tolerance: all components of the Data Ingestion should overcome faults to maintain the system’s availability.

In the next section we present the architecture that ensures that the requirements above are satisfied. The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the overall architecture, and details on the individual components. Section 3 focuses on the data ingested and the computations on the edge. Section 4 describes the cloud-based stream processing algorithms. Section 5 deals with an evaluation of the scalability of the proposed solution. Section 6 discusses the related work while Section 7 wraps up the main conclusions.

2 Architecture

In our solution, data ingestion and runtime analysis relies on a hybrid edge-and cloud-based framework that is responsible for receiving data from multiple sources (which, in our case, are mainly sensors but also cover EHR and other data sources), performing any data manipulation and analysis tasks required potentially on the edge, and transferring them into a centralised location for further offline analysis. Figure 1 shows an overview of the architecture. It consists of 4 main components:

1. **Edge Component:** this runs on Raspberry PIs, which are installed in the patients’ homes. It receives data from a set of different sensors (described in detail in Section 3.2). After ensuring the quality of the data (e.g., through outlier removal when measurements exceed predefined limits) some basic aggregations may be computed (e.g., calculation of the average heart rate in the last hour), complex event processing may be applied for runtime pattern detection and then, the collected data are published to the cloud-based DIRAP via an MQTT Server.
2. **MQTT³:** it is a simple messaging protocol and a lightweight “publish and subscribe” standard. It is considered a particularly effective and efficient solution for IoT applications. In its implementations, the MQTT Broker is a core component and is responsible for handling up to millions of concurrently connected MQTT Clients. MQTT clients run on the edge.
3. **Cloud Component:** this is the core DIRAP component and is responsible for collecting, extracting and analysing data from different types of sources,

³<https://mqtt.org/>

Fig. 1: Overview of the Data Ingestion Pipeline

process them and transfer them via the Message Bus to a backend storage. The two modules that comprise the cloud component are (i) the REST API that is responsible for handling batch/offline data and (ii) the Streaming Engine that manages the online data stream and is implemented using Apache Flink.⁴ Both modules are further elaborated in Section 2.1.

4. **Message Bus:** it provides the main means for the various components to exchange messages. In our implementation, Apache Kafka⁵ is used, which is an open-source distributed event streaming platform, widely used in the industry sector, for high-performance data pipelines, streaming analytics, data integration, and mission-critical applications. Like MQTT, Kafka uses a publish/subscribe protocol, which dynamically provides definitions of new topics, for more flexibility.

DIRAP interacts also with a cloud-based data warehouse (DW) distributed infrastructure capable of storing both structured and unstructured data. This is used to guarantee flexible storage and communication as well as intelligent management of the stored data. For the secure DW's implementation, the Open Distro for Elastic Search (ODFE)⁶ was used, enhanced with the security plugin. However, DW details are out of our scope, since we focus on the runtime processing module as offered by DIRAP.

⁴<https://flink.apache.org/>

⁵<https://kafka.apache.org/>

⁶<https://opendistro.github.io/for-elasticsearch/>

Below, we provide more details about the cloud component and the ingestion pipelines.

2.1 Cloud component tasks and interconnections

The main module of the Cloud Component is the Streaming Engine. It is responsible for handling the cleaning, transformation, and processing of the raw data sent by the Edge Component or directly submitted by healthcare professionals via the Message Bus. As already mentioned, it is implemented on top of Apache Flink, which is an open-source distributed continuous stream processing framework that provides real-time processing with fault-tolerant mechanisms called checkpoints. Flink is scalable by design. It can also be deployed on more than one computing nodes, thus creating a Flink Cluster to benefit from massive parallelism and attain scalability. The different jobs developed and executed on top of the Flink Cluster in our DIRAP solution can be broadly classified in the following categories:

- **Pre-processing**, which includes deduplication, consistency checks and simple data aggregations.
- **Analysis Algorithms**, which includes streaming outlier detection, trend calculation and detection of arbitrary sequences.
- **Model Execution**, which applies a trained Neural Network model over stream data.

The aforementioned developed Flink jobs facilitate the ingestion and processing of heterogeneous data in real-time, meeting the requirements (**R1**, **R2**) and will be presented in detail in Section 3. Additionally, as described above, Apache Flink, Apache Kafka and MQTT are scalable by design, i.e. they inherently support the deployment of more instances to get the advantage of massive parallelism. Thus their combination provides the scalability that is required for the Big Data scenarios (**R3**). These methods also have embedded mechanisms to guarantee fault tolerance, i.e., to overcome faults, maintain their availability and guarantee that no data are lost. Therefore, DIRAP that is built on top of these technologies has inherited their fault tolerance properties (**R4**).

The second cloud module, apart from MQTT and Kafka, is the REST API, which is used to handle the batch and offline data. It is a cloud-based REST API, based on Spring Boot⁷. The Spring boot framework creates powerful standalone applications and provides tools to enable integration with different components, like Apache Kafka. Protecting the confidentiality of patient information (Fernández-Alemán et al, 2013; Rodrigues et al, 2013) is highly essential. The various components of the DIRAP should communicate in a safe way. The Streaming Engine, the REST API and the MQTT are deployed in the same environment and thus can communicate safely using the local network. On the other hand, the edge computing devices (Raspberry PIs) are installed at the patients' houses and need to get authenticated by UAA Proxy Service and use a secure TLS communication in order to publish messages to

⁷<https://spring.io/projects/spring-boot>

the MQTT Server. Both the REST API and the Flink cluster are communicating with the Message Bus to publish information, from batch and stream data, respectively. To address the security issues at this point, two different security mechanisms are used. First, there is a firewall that accepts connections only from trusted sources (like the environment that the components were deployed). Secondly, each component must initialize a secure TLS connection with the Message Bus with the use of self-signed certificates.

2.2 Ingestion Pipelines

Based on the requirements described in **R1**, there are two main data types, one that refers to streaming data and one that deals with batch/offline data. Thus DIRAP encapsulates two data ingestion pipelines accordingly. Furthermore, in order to calculate some specific variables, there is a need for an alternative pipeline, which retrieves historical data from the DW component so that these offline data are combined with streaming data.

More specifically, the first ingestion pipeline refers to data that arrive through the edge devices (streaming data). The heterogeneous data from all the sensors that monitor the patients' behaviour and QoL are ingested to Flink through the MQTT broker. In between ingestion from the relevant sensor gateways and transmission to the MQTT broker, the data are pre-processed on the edge to ensure their quality. Pre-processing consists of detecting and removing duplicate values, fixing timestamps and data aggregations, like extracting the mean and standard deviation from each type of sensor. Complex pattern detection is also enabled. This phase runs on the edge but it is also complemented by similar processes on the cloud. In the next phase, more advanced analytics algorithms, like trend calculation and outlier detection, are employed. The pre-processed and aggregated data along with the output of the analytics algorithms are published to the Message Bus (Apache Kafka), guaranteeing their availability to other components and their permanent storage to the DW.

The second pipeline refers to the ingestion of batch or offline data, such as the EHR (Electronic Health Records) ingested by clinicians and PROMS ingested by the patients, that are directly published to the Message Bus. It is essential for both collaborative and multimodal data analysis, since most data provided by healthcare professionals are not streaming. It is supported by the REST API that has been developed and is deployed on the Cloud as discussed above. The users, both clinicians and patients, must be authorized in order to submit any request. In our exact prototype solution, the authentication is handled by an IDP (Identity Data Provider). The ingested records are pre-processed, duplicate records are removed, and faulty timestamps are fixed.

In addition, there are some scenarios in which historical data are required for advanced analytics like detecting outliers and changing points. Thus, DIRAP has a third pipeline that is responsible for extracting data from the DW. Flink periodically sends a request to the DW through the Message Bus, in order to retrieve historical values, like the average heart beats per patient in the last month. The requested information is published back to the Message

Bus from the DW component, which is then read and stored in the main memory of the Flink job. This enables the historical data to be used in real-time and streaming analytics.

Overall, the DIRAP system is inspired by (and is very close to) the Kappa Architecture, which provides processing for both stream and offline data within a single technology stack. The alternative would be the Lambda Architecture, which has been used in state-of-the-art solutions in the field of medical monitoring (Vitabile et al, 2019) and uses different pipelines to process batch and streaming data. Using the same code to process both types of input render the implementation simpler and easier to maintain. Also, in cases of large batches of data, e.g., processing an extensive portion of the data stored in the Data Warehouse, reading them in parallel and processing them using streaming techniques is significantly more efficient than loading them all together at once.

3 Data and Edge Processing

In accordance to **R1**, the data that are ingested by the DIRAP consist of wearable sensors, smart weight scales, home monitoring devices on the one hand and PROMS and EHR on the other. The edge part of the described framework is responsible for the initial collection, pre-processing and analysing of the monitoring data, which are then forwarded to the cloud via MQTT, while the offline-batch data are directly pushed to the cloud via the cloud-based REST API. In the next sections, we will briefly describe the edge component key components and then present the type of data that are collected from both the Edge and the cloud-based REST API.

3.1 Edge Component Description

In DIRAP, the edge component links the monitoring devices with the cloud-component. It is hosted on Raspberry Pis that are installed at each patient's home. Its main purpose is to collect, process and finally push the data coming from the edge monitoring devices (sensors) to the Cloud. The various sensors currently supported will be presented in the next section. Moreover, the edge computing component performs pre-processing and aggregation on the data streams before forwarding the data to the cloud via the MQTT component.

The edge component consists of (i) a REST API, which is a service that exposes specific endpoints with respect to the available data sources, where the sensors can make post requests to send data that they have already collected, and (ii) a streaming data processing engine. The data are passed through the processing pipeline, where they are pre-processed and aggregated. Pre-processing involves removing null values, extracting the values from specified fields and transforming the structure of the different data sources into a pre-defined one. Additionally, more advanced analytics might be applied on the processed data like detecting arbitrary patterns in the collected data, using Complex Event Processing (CEP).

The main rationale is to provide computational capabilities close to the patient with a view to benefiting from location-awareness, low latency and reduced network usage. Note that, in DIRAP, we are not interested in employing mobile devices for processing on the edge, and thus we do not have to deal with common problems in mobile settings, such as energy efficiency and optimized routing [Aazam et al \(2021\)](#); [Quasim \(2021\)](#); [Comito and Talia \(2017\)](#).

3.2 Edge Ingested Data

In our implementation, the patient’s sensors include a FitBit Charge 4⁸ wristband, a Withings Body+ weight scale⁹ with body composition analysis capability and a t-shirt with an integrated sensor for a subset of patients (MoveSense sensor¹⁰). Data collection from IoT and location systems is performed using a set of location sensors combined with a specific gateway, which is further described later on. Finally, a UV (Ultraviolet Radiation) index measurement provided by the OpenUV service¹¹ has also been integrated in the Fitbit Data Model. All the sensors except the wristband are placed at home, and data are available during the period patients spend indoors. Patients wear the wristband during the whole day inside and outside the home, which is synced with the 3rd-party cloud. Physical activity, heart rate, sleep patterns, and so on are measured continuously. Devices such as the weight scale with body composition analysis are used daily, and hence measurements are less frequent. A specialized mHealth mobile application requests data from 3rd party app, e.g., Withings, OpenUV, Fitbit, through the day or intraday APIs. Intraday API provides data in a specific time interval enabling access to the data, e.g., the number of steps in five minutes’ intervals. Location and IoT sensors are directly synced to tailor-made gateways deployed on the edge computing devices, i.e., a Raspberry PI. The data that are collected by all these devices have been reviewed and identified by clinicians and data scientists as sources that could possibly contribute to the creation of effective models for the QoL of cancer patients.

3.2.1 Home Location Sensors

The Location sensors that have been used in our work, provide the real-time location for the user inside the home. The Kit is composed of several location sensors, a door sensor and a tag. Specific tags are used to identify the patient from other persons living in the same house. These devices are endowed with the corresponding firmware for controlling the communication and the registry of trigger events. Additionally, in our case, smart Plugs that track the state of an appliance (which, in our case, are TVs) have also been integrated. The Location Sensors gateway is a component that receives the data from the

⁸<https://www.fitbit.com/global/uk/products/trackers/charge4>

⁹<https://www.withings.com/us/en/body-plus>

¹⁰<https://www.movesense.com/>

¹¹<https://www.openuv.io/>

sensors and is deployed on an edge device. The data are then forwarded to the Edge Analytics Engine, which in turn forwards them to the cloud via the DIRAP. The data are in the form of individual JSON files, each of which includes specific location-related information as follows:

- **Distinct position:** sent every time the patient changes room or every 5 minutes if no room change has occurred. It includes information for the room, the exact time the patient entered it and the number of activations that have been recorded.
- **Aggregated positions and total time in each room:** sent once per day, once the day has finished (23:59:59). They include information on the exact time, the number of the activations per room and the total time in minutes that the patient has spent in each room.
- **Ambient measurements:** sent every time an ambient measurement is taken. The frequency is configurable. The ambient measurements refer to the humidity and the temperature of the room where the ambient sensor is located.
- **Appliance state:** sent every time the TV is switched on or off. It includes information for the exact time the change of status has been recorded, the type of appliance and its state.
- **Faulty sensor detection:** sent every time a fault of a sensor is detected, or when a fault is solved. The sensors share names with the list of rooms and the list of appliances. The status is either “started” or “ended” (accordingly to the state of the error). The possible faults are “Disconnected”, “Battery” and “Signal”.

Although a large part of these data are forwarded to the cloud as is, there are still basic calculations and processing that take place in the edge analytics engine. Such examples include either the direct assignment of values extracted by the location sensors gateway to specific variables that have been identified as useful by clinicians, or the calculation of such variables on the fly (e.g. number of total sleep interruptions during the night). More precisely, instead of just pushing all the information collected by the gateway to the cloud, the edge analytics engine filters, calculates and pushes only the information that have been evaluated as useful. This operation facilitates the process of the model creation, simplifies the data analysis and decreases the need of further extensive processing in the cloud. Nevertheless, taking into consideration the limitations posed by the available computational resources on the edge, the calculation of some more complex variables takes place in Flink and is thoroughly presented in the next sections. Finally, more complex pattern detection is enabled through an edge-hosted complex event processing module; this functionality, which is available for all types of ingested data, is also deployed on the cloud so that it can be applied to data streams from multiple patients.

3.2.2 Smart sensors streaming data

Patients wear a Fitbit Charge smartwatch, which can collect multiple types of data related to their activities, heart rates, and so on, during all day and night. All these data are presented in the official documentation of the Fitbit API.¹² Delving deeper into the Fitbit official data schema is beyond the scope of this work. However, clinicians have identified many variables that are not provided directly by the Fitbit API. For this reason, further calculations take place both on the edge and the cloud at runtime. Thus, the data that are pushed to the cloud can be classified in two distinct types:

- Raw: The data are pushed to cloud as provided by the mobile mHealth App.
- Processed on the Edge: Fitbit data are further processed on the edge, new variables are calculated, and then pushed to the cloud.

Similar to the case of locations sensor data, the data processing that takes place on the edge includes the mapping of values measured by the smartwatch to specific variables and the calculation of some variables, whose values are not directly provided by the Fitbit API. However, the calculation of these additional variables is not trivial. Such an example is the computation of the number of times the patient has taken a nap and their total duration. The computation process includes the following steps: The edge analytics engine receives a JSON file that includes information about the patient's sleep. The "sleep" object contains a value that corresponds to whether this sleep was the main one or not and another one that refers to the duration of this sleep. If the sleep is not the main one, we consider it as a nap. In this case the edge analytics engine retrieves the latest daily saved value from a main memory database running on the edge (which is Redis¹³ in our prototype) for the naps count variable and increases it by one. At the same time, the duration of naps variable is also retrieved and gets updated, by adding the duration of the latest nap. The variables are continuously updated, whenever a new JSON object that has sleep information is received. At the end of the day, these variables are transferred to the cloud. Variables whose computation is even more complex are calculated on Flink.

Apart from the data provided by the Fitbit API, the patient id and a UV index measurement have also been integrated in the data schema mentioned above. This UV index measurement is provided by the OpenUV API (Open UV API). The OpenUV service provides the UV index measurement at specific timestamps, according to the location of the patient (which remains undisclosed).

Patients also use a smart body scale (Withing Body+) once per day. This smart scale provides information not only for the weight, but for the body composition as well (body fat, fat free mass, muscle mass, hydration, and so on). The data generated from the smart scale include many variables that clinicians have marked as important. However, similar to the Fitbit case, some

¹²<https://dev.fitbit.com/build/reference/web-api/>

¹³<https://redis.io/>

of the variables that have been identified by clinicians are not directly provided by the Withing API (Withings API¹⁴). Most of these required variables are calculated on the edge. Still, there are some variables, the calculation of which takes place on the cloud (Flink). The raw data, as collected by the mHealth App, are pushed unaltered directly to the cloud. The rest of the variables, which include additional calculation on the edge, after being processed on the edge are then pushed to the cloud.

Finally, a subset of patients are also using a t-shirt with a movesense integrated sensor. The sensor generated data are collected by the Movesense gateway, which is installed on the edge computing device (Raspberry Pi). Since no further calculations are required, the data are forwarded to the cloud as is. The data include information for the Heart Rate and the RR interval at a specific timestamp and the 3-axis accelerometer values.

3.3 Offline and Batch Data

Among the main contributions of the solution as a whole is the capability to combine multimodal and heterogeneous data to assess the QoL of cancer patients and enable collaborative care delivery. Streaming and evolving measurement data are combined with offline data such as the patients' past Electronic Health Records (EHR) or data that are produced within a certain (longer) period, like the PROMS (recorded by filling the questionnaires included in the mobile mHealth app). Thus, one functionality that also needs to be supported by the DIRAP is the ability to ingest such data. The EHR data are moved to the data warehouse via the DIRAP by allowing the health-care professionals to make post requests to the REST API deployed on the cloud. As for the PROMS, a similar approach is followed but, in this case, the data are posted by the mHealth App to the cloud-based REST API. Below, we briefly describe the type of data for each case.

Both EHR and PROMS data are in simple JSON format and include information regarding each patient. In the case of EHR data, the information provided depends on the available past medical records per patient group. This means that, although the whole list of EHR data includes more than 80 variables, the per-patient group includes just a subset of them rather than all. Similar to the EHR data, PROMS are also pilot-specific in our implementation. Nevertheless, among the PROMS that are collected, there are five that are common to all patients, namely PHQ-4, ESAS-r, MARS, VES-13, LASA. In any case, the content and type of these offline data do not affect the DIRAP and do not require any further design specifications since none of these data is further processed on the cloud. The corresponding JSON files both for EHR and PROMS are collected via the REST API and forwarded to the DW, using the DIRAP.

¹⁴<https://developer.withings.com/api-reference/#operation/dropshipmentv2-update>

4 Computations on the cloud

All cloud-based computations adhere to the same template, namely they retrieve potentially streaming data from a message broker, run a Flink job, which processes incoming records possibly using a window, and send the outcome to the appropriate output topics of the message bus. This abstraction, which is provided by our framework, enables the development of different modules that solve essential problems in the domain of health care. Combining the high volume of measurements coming from multiple sources referring to several patients, it facilitates the extraction of inter-patient, i.e., collaborative, information about the patients' normal behavior and can be further used to support higher-level functionality and advanced algorithms e.g., a recommendation engine.

In addition to the pre-processing and data aggregation (Section 4.1), DIRAP supports analysis scenarios that include arbitrary pattern detection using CEP (Complex Event Processing) Section 4.2, anomaly detection (Section 4.4), trend analysis and application of Neural Networks models on streaming data (Sections 4.5 and 4.6, respectively). In the remaining of this section, we briefly describe the implemented methods, we present the relevant context of the state-of-the-art in healthcare, and provide examples.

4.1 Data Pre-Processing and Aggregation

4.1.1 Timestamps

The various sensors that were presented in Section 3 have different schema and use different formats in their representations. One of the most important field that is common to all sensor data and is independent of our specific prototype is the timestamp, because it is required for the majority of the online analytics methods. In our solution, the specified timestamp format is according to the ISO8601 standard: "yyyy-MM-ddTHH:mm:ssZ", where yyyy is the year, MM is the month, dd is the day, HH represent the hours, mm the minutes and ss the seconds (e.g., "2021-11-31T10:12:55Z"). DIRAP ensures the consistency across the data sent from various sensors. Therefore, all the timestamps are changed to the corresponding ISO8601 format though a specific Flink job.

Another pre-processing task deals with the difference between the time that the measurement was taken and the time that the metrics are ingested in the DIRAP. These two timestamps are almost identical if the patient is at home, but if the patient goes for an outdoor walk for example, the wristband will take measurements, e.g., the heart rates, but these metrics will not be ingested until the patient returns home and a connection can be established. Both timestamps are essential for the online analytics: the first one is used to provide real-time notifications and the second one is used for the trend analysis.

4.1.2 Deduplication and Consistency Checks

It is important for the DIRAP to ensure the accuracy of the ingested data. A faulty measurement can cause the system to send wrong signals, while a missing value can cause the algorithms to crash. The DIRAP solution provides mechanisms to deal with some of the most common problems regarding the values of the ingested data.

Firstly, each measurement should be ingested exactly once, so that the effectiveness of the methods is guaranteed. Messages from MQTT could be sent more than once, due to sensor's or Raspberry's error. The procedure of removing multiple instances of the same message is known as deduplication. In Flink, this is implemented with the help a sliding window lasting a predefined number of seconds (set to 3 in our prototype). If the same message is received more than once in this window, it is discarded as a duplicate.

Secondly, missing values can cause algorithms to misbehave or even crash. Thus all the messages with missing values are discarded. Finally, each sensor measurement is associated with some boundaries according to its type, i.e., the range in which the value is considered valid. A humidity sensor, for example, is expected to have a value between 0 and 100. Out of these boundaries, the value is considered faulty and is discarded. Since the information for the boundaries might not be available for every sensor, the basic statistics for every type of sensor (mean value and standard deviation) across all patients can be used as a guidance to determine the upper and lower limits.

4.1.3 Data Aggregation

Data Aggregation is the process of gathering raw data and deriving a summarization that is more easily consumable and comprehensive. Most often, this summarization is a statistical analysis of the raw input. This is an essential step in the initial processing phase, since it provides the first insights into the patient behavior, so that both developers and domain experts can have a better understanding of the data. Additionally, the aggregated data can be used as input for more advanced algorithms. For example, they can be used to determine the normal and abnormal behaviour of a sensor.

Most of the aggregations, like getting the average heart rate of a patient in a 6-hour interval, take place in the Edge Analytics Engine, in order to reduce the amount of unnecessary data and increase the efficiency of the analytics methods. The data aggregation that occurs in the Flink component is mostly focused on aggregating data that come from different patients and enabling collaborative care delivery, something that cannot be done on the edge. It produces input that is used in other procedures.

DIRAP has a procedure that performs statistical analysis over the sensor measurements, both at an intra-patient and at an inter-patient level. Intra-patient statistics refer to the calculation of basic statistics (such as, min, max, x, mean, and standard deviation) for every sensor and every patient, which gives specific insights into the behaviour of a certain patient. For example,

the preferable temperature of the patient’s home, which can be used later to detect a correlation between home temperature and quality of sleep, in order to provide suggestions to improve it. On the other hand, inter-patient statistics refer to the basic statistics of the measurements from a sensor across all patients and is used to get insights into the general behaviour of a specific type of sensor. The inter-patient statistics for the temperature sensor include the mean temperature of all the patients’ houses, thus can be utilized to detect anomalies, deviations from the mean value, and provide warnings for probable causalities (open window, faulty sensor etc.). In Flink, both aggregations are implemented using a sliding window of a predifed window and slide size; in our prototype we employ 7-days windows with a single slide per day. This provides enough information to capture the normal behavior and detect a change point early.

4.2 CEP (Complex Event Processing)

In many scenarios, the aim is to identify arbitrary complex phenomena comprising a sequence of events in real-time. Examples of such scenarios is when a patient took his medication more than once a day or her pulse is rapidly increasing. Both these scenarios can be supported through detecting a pattern of events within a certain time interval. In order for these phenomena to be identified, some rules are generated and used. These rules specify the conditions that must co-exist for the phenomenon occurrence to be declared. CEP is an evolving technology that enables the extraction of this kind of information from infinite incoming event streams. DIRAP provides an abstract implementation along with an example to show its effectiveness and demonstrate how it can be used for similar scenarios.

CEP techniques are mainly used for scenarios in which there is a large volume of events occurring and latency requirements are incredibly low.¹⁵ Since CEP matches continuously incoming events against a pattern and relevant or critical situations can be identified and reported in real-time, it allows for taking proactive actions when early warning signs are detected. Therefore, CEP is inextricably linked to monitoring and sophisticated online applications, as evidenced by the number of works that exploit it for monitoring in real-world applications, such as (Graubner et al, 2018; Ramoly et al, 2018; Dhillon et al, 2018; Roldán et al, 2020; Loreti et al, 2019; Kulshrestha and Durbha, 2020; Khazael et al, 2021; Lan et al, 2019). The major application areas of CEP, apart from health systems, are sensor networks, RFID systems in retail, transport networks, and IoT networks, e.g., (Ma et al, 2019; Peng et al, 2019; Bok et al, 2018). In the area of security, associated also with other fields, the authors in (Roldán et al, 2020) proposed a technique that combined CEP with machine learning, in order to detect in real-time various IoT security attacks. The proposed architecture was applied to a healthcare IoT network scenario. (Rahmani

¹⁵We mainly provide this functionality on the cloud, since Flink is notoriously good for low-latency streaming applications, however, we have also incorporated CEP functionality on the edge if required.

et al, 2021) used CEP for increasing the healthcare quality of patients, by performing instant data analysis to early diagnose diseases and pick the most effective treatment, something that also DIRAP provides. (Ramoly et al, 2018) proposed a framework for healthcare in smart homes to monitor, interact and keep company to patients, while (Dautov et al, 2019) attempted to tackle the problem of data fusion, proposing a distributed hierarchical architecture for smart homes that accepts data from multiple sources, processes them on-the-fly and helps taking decisions to improve the performance of public healthcare services. In (Riboni et al, 2016), a behaviour analysis system named LOTAR that combines machine-learning algorithms with knowledge-based and data mining is proposed; this system aims to detect early signs of cognitive decline. The anomaly behaviour is divided into short-term and long-term anomalies. In our work, the focus is on the short-term type, while long term will be discussed later in the next section. In LOTAR, short-term anomaly detection is handled by a rule-based approach. Essentially, descriptions from clinicians have been translated to a set of rules that are used to determine if a patient’s behaviour is normal or not. In order to implement this functionality in an online system that handles hundreds of patients and provides real-time analytics, these rules need to be transformed to patterns and handled by a CEP engine. In (Dhillon et al, 2018) authors describe an end-to-end architecture for Remote Patient Monitoring (RPM) as-a-service, in which data from the patient are collected from different sensors to patient’s mobile phone, where also CEP is performed, in order to detect patterns and provide insights for possible health problems before the data will be propagated into the responsible hospital for further analysis. Similar applications are supported by our solution, which furthers encapsulates CEP functionality in a broader scalable analysis framework.

For example, let us use the data from the Location sensors to create a meaningful pattern that would be useful to detect. Patients should have breakfast in the morning, so they can have the necessary energy for the rest of the day. If a patient skips the breakfast, the system should create an alarm and notify the caregiver. A possible pattern that the system can continuously look for may have the following form:

Pattern = (Bedroom, maybe(Bathroom), not(Kitchen), Living_room)

The pattern above implies that the patient will wake up, maybe visits the bathroom, and then goes straight to the living room without passing from the kitchen. Whenever, this pattern is detected, it constitutes a strong indicator that she skipped the breakfast. Several other patterns can be active simultaneously. DIRAP uses the FlinkCEP¹⁶ library to describe the patterns and apply them on top of the Flink streams. In this example, the stream from the MQTT topic corresponding to the Location sensors is used as input. Since the events are referring to all the patients, a group by the patient id is required. Next, the defined pattern is applied on the streams. Once a match is found, a report

¹⁶<https://ci.apache.org/projects/flink/flink-docs-release-1.13/docs/libs/cep/>

will be created to a topic in the Message Bus, containing the timestamps of the first and last event in the pattern, the patient id, and the type of the alert.

4.3 Runtime detection of arbitrary correlations

Collecting data from multiple sources is one of the main strong points of the DIRAP. Using the different sensors, clinicians have better understating of a patient's life and so they can provide more accurate advice. Another advantage of using data from various sources is that meaningful correlations between the different types of measurements can be analysed. For example, advanced analysis may be based on the computation of the correlation between an increase in the accelerometer and the number of steps, or the temperature in the bedroom and the quality of the sleep. These correlations can be used to identify patterns and detect abnormalities.

In Section 4.1.3, it is discussed how the basic statistics are computed per sensor for all patients (inter-patient) and per sensor per patient (intra-patient). These statistics can be used to create rules based on the correlations between the different metrics in order to detect behaviour patterns. Two examples are presented below, one for a behaviour pattern across all patients and another one that is focused on a particular patient.

Example 1: “As the outside temperature increases, so does the outdoor steps”. That is, people tend to take long walks and exercise outside when the weather is good. This is common among most of the patients and thus this rule captures the normal behaviour. If a patient does not go outside in a sunny day, it can be considered as an indicator of lack of physical exercise or even possible signs of early depression.

Example 2: “As the number of indoor steps increases, so does the number of transitions between different rooms in the home”. This rule once again describes the normal behaviour based on the correlation of two different inputs. An increase in the number of steps without the increase of transitions might be an indicator of nervous pacing, especially if it is followed by an increase in the heart rate. Another explanation would be that the patient may be exercising on a treadmill. On the other hand, in case that the number of transitions is increasing without the increase of steps, an assumption would be that the sensor responsible for the steps' counting is malfunctioning.

These two examples simply show how correlations between different metrics can be used as indicators for a pattern behaviour. The combination of knowledge-based rules with simple statistics can be a powerful analytical tool. The output of arbitrary correlations is published to the Message Bus. The implementation conforms to a generic template that makes it trivial to append new rules.

4.4 Outlier Detection

An outlier is “an observation which deviates so much from other observations as to arouse suspicions that it was generated by a different mechanism”

(Hawkins, 1980). The outlying data often contains useful information about the abnormal behaviour, which is the reason that is used in applications such as intrusion detection (Jiang et al, 2006), credit card fraud (Fawcett and Provost, 2002) and so on (Aggarwal, 2017).

In the previous sections, we presented how CEP and correlations between measurements can be utilized to detect outliers using rules. This type of approach has both advantages and disadvantages. The main advantages of these methods are the explainability and the simplicity, i.e., the ability to explain why an event is abnormal and the fact that it is easy to implement and modify them. On the contrary, the main disadvantage of rule-based techniques, in general, is that they require domain knowledge, i.e., someone with expertise in the field to explicitly describe the rules that need to be detected. It is hard, even for an expert, to describe all the possible scenarios of anomaly behaviour, and even if that was possible, these rules do not take account of diversions in order to adapt as time progresses.

Anomaly detection has been used in various scenarios in the health care domain. In (Šabić et al, 2021) and (Pereira and Silveira, 2019), both supervised and unsupervised outlier detection methods are used to find anomalies in the patients' heart rate. Additionally, in (Ijaz et al, 2020), detecting and removing outliers is shown to have a positive impact on the performance of clustering methods. Another example of using anomaly detection techniques to protect sensitive medical data is presented in (Mohamed et al, 2019), where jamming attacks between the sensors (for Electrocardiogram and Electromyogram) and the processing unit are detected and the intrusion is cancelled.

In (Riboni et al, 2016), the authors describe a state-of-the-art approach for long-term anomaly detection using historical data. In order to detect a change in the patient's habits, they compare the behaviour of the last n days with the m previous days, where n and m are variables set by experts. From the m days, they extract frequent patterns, describing patient's routines, and then compare them with the current routines. If the difference is larger than a threshold, then the current behaviour is reported as anomalous. Following that approach, we implemented two different techniques for anomaly detection based on previous events. These methods provide a more robust way to detect outliers, without the need to predefine what is considered to be an "anomalous" behaviour, as required in the rule-based techniques.

The first method is an implementation of MCOD (Kontaki et al, 2016) in massively parallel streaming systems as described in (Toliopoulos et al, 2020b). MCOD is a continuous outlier monitoring algorithm, based on sliding windows. Following the typical definition of anomalies in distance-based outlier detection, if an event in the stream has at least k neighbours in a distance smaller than R , in a given window, then this event is characterized as inlier; otherwise, it is reported as an outlier. Every time the window progresses, new events are added to the slide and some of the previous ones are deleted. That means that an event can change from inlier to outlier and vice versa, during its lifecycle. This approach helps the algorithm to understand shifts in the

monitored behaviour; this can be related to a problem known as Change Point Detection (CPD), although in general distance-based outlier detection is more generic than CPD. A state-of-the-art approach presented in (Aminikhanghahi et al, 2018) detects change points in high-dimensional time series in real-time, showing the necessity of these solutions in medical monitoring systems.

The MCODE-based outlier detection algorithm employed in DIRAP can be used, for example, to monitor the daily steps of the patients. The daily steps for a patient having a healthy life would be somewhere around to a few thousands. If this patient has an accident and sprain her ankle for example, the steps will be reduced close to zero. Using a sliding window of 10 days, a k equal to 3 and a distance equal to 1000 in the algorithm will result in reporting this behaviour as abnormal in the first four days of the injury (because there will be less than three measurements close to zero) and then consider this behaviour as the new normal, until she recovers. This method is used for anomaly detection along with behaviour shifts. The abstract implementation makes it easy to add the outlier detection on top of any stream, as long as the three required parameters are defined, namely window size W , R and k assuming that the slide is fixed to once per day (although the slide is also configurable). The outlier events are published to the Message Bus to be available to other components and also to be persisted in the DW.

Additionally, a second streaming outlier method has been developed in the context of DIRAP. Historical data that represent the normal behaviour, are extracted from the DW, as described in Section 2.2. Then a comparison is made between this information and the current state of the patient and if the difference exceeds a threshold, then the current behaviour is reported as abnormal and published to the Message Bus. For example, a patient that takes medication to decrease her heart beats has an average heart rate of 70 b/m in the last month, with a standard deviation of 10. If this patient does not take his medication one day, the beats will increase to 85-95. The algorithm will request for the last 10 days the average heart rate and the standard deviation. If the current average is greater than the historic one plus k times the standard deviation, it will be reported as outlier (k is set to 2 in our prototype). The parameters that these algorithms require need a fine tuning at the first time but they provide useful insights in the behaviour of the patients, without the requirement of explicitly defining the patterns. Parameter tuning is largely mitigated by allowing multiple parameters to be checked concurrently, as reported in (Toliopoulos et al, 2020a).

4.5 Trend Calculation

Trend analysis refers to the collection and processing of data in an attempt to spot patterns in the patients' underlying behaviour. It can be used as an indicator in order to predict future events or detect changes in the behaviour. Trend analysis has been used in various applications like analyzing stock market (Yin et al, 2017), predicting security exploitations (Browne et al, 2000),

Fig. 2: Example of heart rate trend

and so on. Furthermore, calculating trends has been utilized by several different applications related to healthcare. The authors in (Virag et al, 2007) propose a method that utilizes the trend for both blood pressure and heart rate to predict vasovagal syncope. Sliding window analysis over heart rate is also used in (Li et al, 2018), as a descriptor of HRV (Heart Rate Variability) in obstructive sleep apnea. An exponential weighted moving average over heart rate is used in (Yang et al, 2006) to detect changes. Predictions are made based on the trend and once new values that deviate significantly from the predicted ones are received, a change point is reported. Apriori algorithms combined with temporal trends within different in-patient subgroups, to mine association rules from big data.

Trend analysis is implemented in DIRAP with the use of moving average. The required parameters are the window size and the window slide, as in streaming outlier detection. In Figure 2, the trend of rest heart rate for the last 10 days is calculated, using a window size of 7 days and a window slide of 1 day. The high value of heart rate on the second day may be an indication of a stressful incident in the week ending on that day and most probably 7 days before.

In our implementation, we calculate the trend of different measurements and with different window sizes, in order to enable the integration with various scenarios. For example, we calculate the quality of sleep (time of REM, Light sleep and Deep sleep) using a window size of 7-days with 1-day slide. Using the same parameters, we calculate the trend for weight (BMI, fat percentage, water percentage and muscle percentage) and heart rate (heart rate rest, max heart rate and overnight heart rate). Besides these trends that are required to determine the quality of patients life, there are others that require a smaller window so they can enable near real-time notifications and recommendations, e.g., activity tracking (count of steps and stairs), in which we use an 1-hour window slide with 7-days window size.

4.6 Application of Neural Network Models

Neural Networks (NN) is one of the leading technologies in data analytics. Specifically in the field of health care, NNs have been broadly used. Healthcare organizations are using NN to predict upcoming events in order to better support their decision making (Shahid et al, 2019). Insurance companies have been using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to predict the patient's future cost, by learning the hidden patterns in her behaviour (Morid et al, 2020). Similar to Lifechamps, authors in (Dawar and Kehtarnavaz, 2018) propose a monitoring system based on CNN that used different sensors to capture the transition movements. The capability of NNs to learn patterns makes them suitable for anomaly detection applications. For example, the authors in (Pereira and Silveira, 2019) propose a method to detect anomalous heart beats, based on Autoencoders. In (Arifoglu and Bouchachia, 2019), they use data from temperature, motion, and location sensors to find abnormal behaviour caused by dementia. Data are used to identify activities, such as "Took Medicine" and "Wake up at night", which are then fed to a CNN. CNN is trained to classify sequences of activities as normal or abnormal. Activities repetition and disruption in sleep are some of the patterns that will be reported as anomalies and can indicate that a patient is suffering from dementia.

As discussed in Gomes et al (2019), there are a number of challenges when implementing NN-based machine learning algorithms on streaming data. A main challenge corresponds to the requirement for low latency, as the data should be processed in near real-time with minimal delay, and as such, the model cannot afford to contain complex calculations. Also, as we operate in a real-world scenario, it is possible that a concept drift may occur and the model should be capable of adapting to this change Desale and Shinde (2022). Finally, the models, most of the time, deal with unlabeled data. This can be addressed by either employing unsupervised methods (similar to MCOB described in Section 4.4) or acquiring domain knowledge, which in healthcare applications is required in order to build effective and robust models.

DIRAP facilitates the application of trained models, providing real-time analytics and recommendations for the patients' behaviour. These models can be developed with the help of clinicians using the data stored in the data warehouse. In that way, the domain knowledge is introduced in the building stage of the model. Low latency when applying trained models at runtime is also supported by the massively parallel execution model of Flink. Tolerance and adaptations to concept drifts is naturally supported through periodically retraining the models. Contrary to using continual learning machine learning models Lee and Lee (2020), which introduce additional complexity in the system and increase the memory footprint, we have developed a mechanism that supports the automated deployment of new NN model instances through the Message Bus. The training is performed offline, on top of the DW, and once a new model is available, DIRAP is directly notified and employs it. Some examples of NN models that are supported by and deployed in the DIRAP are (i) a set of algorithms for Big Data processing and prescriptive analytics and (ii)

Fig. 3: Employment of models in the Flink Cluster

the Recommendation engine, a data-driven health recommender system that will help patients improve their QoL and foster healthier habits.

Figure 3 presents how the NNs fit with the rest of the architecture. Streaming data from a specified topic in the Message Bus pass through the NN and the results are published back to the Message Bus in a separate topic.

4.7 An end-to-end walk-through example use case

After having discusses the data ingested and computations enabled, we provide a walk-through end-to-end example of the complete pipeline, as depicted in Figure1. As mentioned in more detail in Section 3, the data that are ingested by the DIRAP originate from multiple and heterogeneous input sources, which consist of wearable sensors, smart weight scales, home monitoring devices on the one hand, and PROMS and EHRs on the other. In our example, we consider the data from the patient’s smart weight scale Withings+, which provides information related to body hydration and fat, muscle and bone mass, weight, and height. These measurement data are collected once per day by a corresponding gateway application, and are sent to the corresponding endpoint of the REST API implemented in the edge component.

The edge component is responsible for receiving and pre-processing the data and converting them into a common format so that it is treated as uniformly as possible. As such, each actual measurement captured by the weight scale is formatted to a key-value pair, including also the timestamp of the measurement, and a unique identifier for this patient, the “patientId”. Except for the extraction of the actual measurements and transformation of the data into key-value pairs, the edge component of DIRAP performs also some basic calculations, such as the computation of the BMI and BMI category based on the weight and height provided by the weight scale. It also performs more advanced analytics like detecting the continual increase of the BMI in a period of time, using CEP technology capable of running on a single core of a Raspberry Pi. All data are then forwarded to the cloud component through the MQTT broker conforming to the publish-subscribe messaging pattern. However, other data, in batch mode, such as EHR and PROMS, are received by Flink through the respective endpoints of the REST API implemented in the cloud component.

All incoming data arrived at Flink are submitted to further process. More specifically, a Flink job processes the data using a time window and sends the outcome to the corresponding output topics of the Message Bus between the Cloud and the Data Warehouse; in DIRAP, the message bus is implemented with Apache Kafka. In the case of the Withings data, the incoming metrics derived by the edge component are processed in order for last 7 days trends regarding all associated measurements to be calculated. Flink receives messages from multiple patients at the same time, and hence, to calculate the personalized last 7 days trends, it groups the messages by the “patientId” included. For example, regarding the weight measurement, DIRAP is capable of calculating the patient’s weight trend or the BMI trend, using a 7-day sliding window. Then, all calculated variables are transmitted to the Data Warehouse, where they are stored for future usage and analysis. Stored data enable more complex calculations, such as monitoring the patient’s weight loss. By using the historical data from the Data Warehouse, we are able to generate a warning if the patient has lost 1-1.5% of his/her weight in the last two weeks.

5 Evaluation of Scalability

Scalability refers to the ability of a system to handle additional workload by adding more resources to the system. Scalability is a requirement for big-data applications. In the systematic review conducted regarding applications of IoT in the field of health care, scalability is described as one of the challenges, since most of the approaches are used in limited scenarios (Kashani et al, 2021).

As presented in Section 4.5, trend is calculated for a large number of variables during the data ingestion. Due to this reason, trend calculation is used as the main procedure to evaluate the scalability of DIRAP. Other proposals behave similarly, whereas extensive results for the scalability of streaming outlier detection using Flink have Flink appeared in Toliopoulos et al (2020b); more generic insights into Flink behavior can be found in publications, such as Carbone et al (2015). Trend calculation requires two parameters, namely the window size, and the window slide. For all the experiments the slide is constant and equal to 1 minute to emulate a (near) real-time scenario that is more demanding than the ones used in practice, since in the most calculated trends, the slide is 1 day. The size of the window varies from 1 to 15 minutes.

The metrics that are used in the evaluation are based on the window processing time, that is the time required to calculate the average value of the measurements inside a window. In order to have real-time analytics, this time has to be less than the window slide, i.e. 1 minute. *Total CPU time* is the maximum time that it takes a thread to calculate trends during an experiment. We have also used the *throughput* metric, which refers to the number of measurements processed in a period and is calculated by dividing the total number of processed measurements by the total CPU time.

In our experiments, we have used a synthetic data stream to stress the system. This stream is generated inside the Flink cluster mimicking the data

Fig. 4: Throughput for different number of input threads and volumes.

ingested from MQTT topics. The generated measurements consist of a patient id (randomly selected using a uniform distribution) and a value, which is a uniformly distributed random number between 0 and 1. For each experiment, the data generator was executed for 30 minutes. The custom data generator uses 3 parameters:

- *DataPerSecond*: number of events generated per second for each thread.
- *Threads*: number of threads, which is the equivalent of number of different MQTT topics.
- *Patients*: number of different (synthetic) patients.

The experiments in Sections 5.1 and 5.2 are executed using a machine with 64GB of RAM and a 2.0GHz CPU with 8 cores and 16 threads. In the last section, we increase the number of Flink nodes, using a cluster, and the specifications are provided in Section 5.3.

5.1 Experiments on number of topics

DIRAP is capable of ingesting data from high volume MQTT topics. In this section, we evaluate the scalability of DIRAP with respect to the number of threads that generate data and the data volume. We vary the number of threads from 1 to 16 (maximum number of threads in the machine), while increasing the generated data per thread from 10K to 50K and then to 100K measurements per second. The number of different patients, the window size and the parallelism are constant across all experiments and equal to 10, 1 minute and 16, respectively.

In Figure 4, we present the throughput for different volumes and input threads. We can observe that for the small volume (10K measurements per second), the throughput increases for threads from 1 to 8, which is enabled by the under-utilization of the resources due to the small amount of data per second. The machine running the experiment has 8 physical cores, so the process cannot be efficiently parallelized using 16 threads causing the throughput

Fig. 5: Total CPU time across all Flink tasks for different number of input threads and volumes.

Fig. 6: Average time to process a window for different volumes

to degrade when increasing the number of threads from 8 to 16. For the other two volumes, the throughput is relatively constant, despite the increase in the volume and input threads and it is varying from 15M to 17.5M measurements per second. This implies that there is no computation bottleneck, and the data can be processed in real-time. This conclusion can be further supported by the findings presented in Figure 5. This figure shows the total CPU time for the different number of threads and volumes. The main observation is that the total CPU time increases linearly with regards to both the number of threads and the data volume. For example, for the highest volume of data (100K measurements per second) the total CPU time while using 4 threads is 15 seconds, and it reaches 30 seconds while doubling the threads. That linearity supports the claim that DIRAP is scalable and can handle big data scenarios.

Complementary to the previous analysis, we present the average processing time per window, as it progresses through the experiments, for the different data volumes in Figure 6. The time increases in the beginning as the windows are initialized with data and then it remains relatively constant. The

Fig. 7: Average time to process window for different window sizes (in minutes).

average times are approximately 60, 300 and 400 milliseconds, respectively, for the three volumes of data to be ingested. The processing time for the 50K measurements per second is 5 times greater than the processing time for the small volume (10K measurements/second), which means that it increases linearly with regards to the data volume. However, as the input data volume is doubled, moving from 50K measurements/second to 100K, the processing time increases less than two times. This observation, along with the capability of Flink to add new nodes at any time, further supports our claim that the DIRAP architecture is scalable and suitable for big data applications.

5.2 Experiments with varying window size and number of patients

In this section, we evaluate how the other 2 parameters, i.e. window size and number of patients affect the performance of the trend analysis. More specifically, we vary the window size from 1 minute to 15 minutes, while maintaining the rest of the parameters constant (patients=10 and threads=1). As the window size increases, more data are required to be stored in the main memory. This experiment was executed in a single machine, thus we had to adjust the data volumes, in order to avoid memory exceptions when examining the greater window sizes. Hence, the 3 data volumes are reduced to 10K, 25K and 50K.

In Figure 7, we present the average CPU time per window in milliseconds. We can observe that the time increases linearly regarding the window size for the same data volume. The same observation can also be made for the data volumes. The average CPU time for the 15-minute window and the 50K measurements per second is twice the average CPU time for the same window size but half the data volume. The main conclusion based on these observations is that the DIRAP scales well with the size of the window.

Fig. 8: Total CPU time for different number of patients.

Machine	CPU	Cores/ Threads	Memory	HD
1	Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2620 v2 @ 2.1GHz	6/12	64G	1 SSD 1TB
2	Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2640 v2 @ 2.1GHz	8/16	64G	1 SSD 1TB
3	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-3770K CPU @ 3.5GHz	4/8	32G	1 SSD 1TB
4	AMD FX(tm)-9370	8/8	32G	1 SSD 1TB

Table 1: Specifications of the different machines in the cluster

Finally, in Figure 8 we show the effect that the number of patients have on the performance of the trend calculation. The number of patients is varying from 10 to 2K, while the volume and window size are maintained constant and equal to 50K measurements/second and 1 minute, respectively. For every patient, Flink creates a logical window, that stores and processes the measurements that refer to this patient. As the number of patients increases from 10 to 1K, the total CPU time also increases. However, for number of patients greater than 1K, there is no significant difference in the total time. Conclusively, the number of patients has no significant impact on the performance of DIRAP for large numbers, which is the case for the scenario that the DIRAP platform aims to support.

5.3 Experiments with more Flink nodes

The previous experiments show that a single machine can handle high data volumes of data to be ingested and analysed on the fly. However, the main alternative to scale a Flink application is to use more nodes, that is more machines that run an instance of a Flink Taskmanager. To evaluate the scalability under such a scenario, we use a cluster of 4 machines for the experiments, and we present their specifications in Table 1. The cluster is heterogenous, i.e. the machines that constitute the cluster are of different types and capabilities.

For all the experiments, we use 16 threads of input data for the 3 different volume settings (10K, 50K and 100K measurements/second). The number of patients is also constant and equal to 10, across all experiments. We start with the first machine and then we add new machines following the same order as the one in the table.

Fig. 9: Throughput for different volumes and number of machines.

Fig. 10: Total CPU time for different volumes and number of machines.

The throughput with respect to the number of employed machines is presented in Figure 9. The main observation is that the throughput increases as the number of machines increases. However, the increase is not linear in the number of the machines, which is attributed to the heterogeneity of the cluster. Even though we can observe that DIRAP scales with respect to the number of nodes, there is a saturation point. By adding more machines, additional latency and network traffic are introduced. If the volume of data is not sufficient, this causes a decrease in the throughput. This is exactly what we can observe in Figure 10, for the small volume, while increasing the machines from 3 to 4. There is a decrease in the throughput even though the number of machines has increased.

In summary, the components that constitute the DIRAP guarantee its capability to scale and handle big data. More specifically, in the previous sections, we showed that DIRAP scales both vertically (as the number of

input threads and data volume increase) and horizontally (by employing more machines – Flink nodes). We have also shown that more machines do not necessarily increase the efficiency of the system.

6 Related Work

In Section 4, we have explained how many state-of-the-art data-driven health-care applications leveraging CEP, outlier detection, neural networks, and so on can be supported by DIRAP. Here, we discuss how DIRAP compares to other state-of-art real-time monitoring and analysis platforms. During the past years, many researchers focused on the design and development of sensing frameworks that could be of help to different health-related scenarios. These frameworks need to meet some key requirements both from the patient’s or the clinician/caregiver’s point-of-view, such as: (i) being non-intrusive, (ii) to respect personal data privacy, (iii) being easily deployed at home, (iv) permitting robust remote monitoring in real-time, and finally, (v) being affordable (both in terms of communications and hardware costs). These mHealth frameworks can be generic or built for a specific purpose and clinical context. Examples of such available platforms include MiningMinds(Banos et al, 2016), AWARE(Ferreira et al, 2015), mCerebrum(Hossain et al, 2017), RADAR-base(Ranjan et al, 2019) and other solutions like Beiwe(Torous et al, 2016), Sensus(Xiong et al, 2016) and LAMP(Torous et al, 2019). In the following, we review the main existing solutions, whereas we refer the reader to (Kumar et al, 2021) for a complete listing of existing proposals.

In the MiningMinds platform paradigm (Banos et al, 2016), a mobile edge computing architecture is adopted, following a distributed implementation for real-time audio event detection related to human behavior. The platform consists of a wireless network of acoustic sensors (microphones) and a central base station for data collection. The central processing unit takes advantage of a GPU (NVIDIA Tegra) to pre-process raw audio signal, extract features and automatically recognize and classify audio events using Support Vector Machines (SVMs). Currently this implementation supports short-term, contextual analysis, completely missing long-term tracking of behavioral patterns. It allows for privacy preservation and real-time monitoring. These are realized by local processing means, without the need of transmitting raw audio signals outside the patient’s home and high-performance computing capabilities so to run efficiently machine learning classification algorithms on the fly. Compared to DIRAP, its main disadvantage is that it lacks an extensible streaming analysis engine and message buses/brokers, with the help of which new sensor measurement data can be easily added to the system.

AWARE (Ferreira et al, 2015) on the other hand, is a mobile, open-source platform that is extensible and its functionality can be replicated across different clinical settings and studies. The focus is mostly on mobile instrumentation and thus extensibility refers to the support for new sensors. Special attention is also put on battery consumption of mobile devices. Moreover, a built-in

System	EA	DT	MS	CA	SCA	Architecture	Scalable	Extensible
DIRAP	✓	B-S	✓	✓	✓	Kappa	✓	✓
MiningMinds		S	✓		NA	✓		
AWARE	✓	S	✓		✓	NA		✓
mCerebrum		S	✓	✓	✓	NA	✓	✓
RADAR-base		S	✓	✓		NA	✓	✓

Notations: **EA**: Edge Analytics, **DT**: Data Type, **B**: Batch, **S**: Streaming, **B-S**:Batch and Streaming, **MS**:Multi-source, **CA**: Cloud Analytics, **SCA**: Support for Custom Analytics, **NA**: Not applicable

Table 2: Comparison of DIRAP against other state-of-the-art approaches

MQTT infrastructure supports the real-time context data exchange between available sensors, apps and servers. As such, AWARE is complementary to our solution, since DIRAP aims to deliver a complete ingestion and streaming analytics solution that runs on both the edge and the cloud.

Another promising proposal is the mCerebrum platform (Hossain et al, 2017), which is an open-source, generalizable and reusable platform that supports high-rate, robust data collections from multiple sensors with real-time assessment of data quality and computation of digital biomarkers. It has been utilized and tested in more than ten research studies with several hundreds of participants and it is estimated that more than 100 TB are to be ingested. The platform’s conceptual architecture is split into three major building blocks, which are: i) the sensing layer, ii) the analysis layer and iii) the action or human interaction layer. On the contrary, DIRAP focuses only on the second layer, however, providing a more powerful, scalable and potentially edge-based solution.

The most recent platform is RADAR-base (Ranjan et al, 2019), which constitutes work-in-progress and stems from the European Union Innovative Medicines Initiative, called Remote Assessment of Disease and Relapse – Central Nervous System (RADAR-CNS) program with the aim to support the in-the-wild collection of high-resolution data at scale. Radar-base has been built with the principles of scalability, extensibility and privacy in mind. It is built on top of Kafka for both ingestion, exchange and processing. Consequently, its analytics engine has less capabilities than the one in DIRAP, as outlined in Section 4, while there is no support for processing on the edge. Finally, the main advantages of the RADAR-base platform according to its development team is that it can meet the requirements of high-throughput, low latency data exchange, real-time data processing and robustness in terms of data quality and minimal data loss; all these aspects are fully covered by DIRAP as well.

Table 2 presents the differences between the solutions discussed above and DIRAP. Most of the other approaches either focus on cloud-based analytics-exclusively or do not focus on analytics at all. AWARE, which is the only method except from DIRAP that provides edge analytics, solves challenges related to energy consumption of monitoring devices, but cannot scale in terms

of analytics workload. DIRAP accounts for both streaming and batch data and focuses on the part after the collection of sensor measurements. Data like EHR and PROMS can also be imported in the system and are processed by the same pipeline as the streaming data (Kappa Architecture). All the other aforementioned systems do not support batch data. Overall, DIRAP is the first end-to-end ingestion and streaming analysis proposal to date that leverages both edge and cloud-based computing resources, supports demanding healthcare applications and is compliant with the kappa architecture, according to which the same software stack is used for both batch and stream data processing.

7 Conclusion

In this work, we describe the Data Ingestion and Runtime Analysis Pipeline (DIRAP) solution that is capable of processing both streaming and batch data using the same technology stack, according to the kappa architecture principles. Moreover, DIRAP performs a wide range of potentially complex runtime analytics on both edge and cloud resources. It is motivated by the need to support frailty monitoring for cancer patients after their treatment, but its functionality can generalize to other similar scenarios. It has been fully prototyped and the main source code will become available at the end of the LifeChamps project. The runtime analysis types supported cover a broad range from simple statistics and correlations, to complex event processing, outlier detection, trend computations and application of machine learning models. The platform is directly used by both patients and healthcare professionals, while data from multiple patients can be combined to provide richer insights. Therefore, DIRAP enables advanced collaborative care delivery. Built on top of technologies like MQTT, Apache Flink and Apache Kafka, it is scalable and fault-tolerant by design, while in this work, we provide concrete evidence regarding its scalability properties.

In the future, we plan to implement more advanced analytics in DIRAP, leverage to a greater extent the built-in capability to apply neural network models and explore in depth the details of all healthcare support scenarios DIRAP is planned to support in the context of the LifeChamps project.

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Declarations

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- Conflict of interest/Competing interests (check journal-specific guidelines for which heading to use)

- Ethics approval: N/A
- Consent to participate: N/A
- Consent for publication: yes
- Availability of data and materials: N/A
- Code availability: the main DIRAP code in the form of pre-prepared Docker images, will become available upon the end of the LifeChamps project.
- Authors' contributions: All authors have actively contributed to the design of the solution and the development of the material described in this work. The system implementation was done by the researchers I. Dimitriadis, I. Mavroudopoulos, S. Kyrama and T. Toliopoulos.

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